

Attributes affecting instructors' performance: springboard for organizational development interventions

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to identify the attributes that motivate the training instructors to perform effectively as a basis in proposing organizational development interventions (ODI) for Philippine Coast Guard-Coast Guard Education Training and Doctrine Command (PCG-CGETDC), Philippine Navy-Naval Education, Training and Doctrine Command (PN-NETDC), and Philippine Merchant Marine Academy-Training Center (PMMA-TC). The survey results identified thirty-one attributes that highly motivate the instructors to perform effectively where no significant difference among the responses was established. Among the top motivational attributes are alignment of professional goals with the organizational goals; communication between head and subordinates; observance of fair work practices; assistance in technical support; clear selection, recruitment, and promotion policies; and existence of evaluation and feedback system and quality management system. Conversely, a significant relationship between the respondents' extent of agreement on the attributes affecting their performance and their profiles was revealed. The training instructors considered twenty-three organizational interventions very important. There is a significant difference between and within their responses as an institution. The strengths-weaknesses-opportunities-threats (SWOT) analysis and other related data, gathered through survey, were utilized to develop the proposed validated ODI for these maritime-related institutions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Everything evolves, as change is the only permanent thing in this world. Organizations must keep abreast of developments to avoid being left behind, including their human resource management (HRM). As Richman [1] depicted, the organization's greatest asset is its human resources. Thus, they are the best instruments for achieving organizational success. But as he discussed, HRM is processed-based, it is more on recruitment, labor relations, health, and safety. HRM needs to transform into human resource development (HRD) to maximize the potential of its human resources. Contrary to HRM, HRD focuses on activities that support behavioral change and learning opportunities for employees to achieve high performance. Given this, organizations must move from the traditional HRM to applying behavioral science to help organizations improve individuals and systems through organizational development (OD). This is supported by Kareem [2] as he stated that OD focuses on improving the individual, group, and the over-all organization through planned interventions and training experiences.

In the study of Khattak *et al.* [3] organizational development interventions (ODI) are divided into four categories: structural, technological, behavioral, and strategic and targeting specific aspects of organizational improvement to enhance employee performance and effectiveness. Additionally, the study highlights that understanding and implementing OD interventions can significantly enhance employability and organizational success. Wu and Preudhikulpradab [4] recommended organization development interventions such as organizational justice, organizational support, training and development, organizational communication and organizational leadership. Augustine *et al.* [5] also emphasized similar OD interventions (ODI) such as teambuilding, intergroup, process consultation, coaching and counseling, career planning, and goal-setting. Verghese [6] explained some of these ODIs, diagnostic activities refer to fact-finding, those activities designed to improve department or unit effectiveness are called team building activities. On the other hand, intergroup activities are designed to improve interdependent group effectiveness. Feedback activities are focused on tools to generate the current state of individuals or institution and are to be used for problem solving activities. Structural activities are designed to improve the organization's design job enrichment, socio-technical design, and others. Coaching and counselling are basically defining goals and how others see themselves and learning new behavior. Life and career planning activities enable the individuals to focus on their lives, career objectives, and the means to achieve them. Finally, the open systems planning related to systematic management and organizational transformation is more on developing the institution's mission statement, and future expectations.

But OD cannot occur without the individuals working towards it. Empowerment is important in an organization for it stimulates employee capabilities. Ordinary employees have positive regards on a work environment with easy access to information and resources, which maximizes their innovative abilities [7]. These individuals, therefore, must be empowered. However, empowering those goes beyond simple resource allocation; they need to have a voice, autonomy, recognition, or new roles.

In the study made by Tran and Hung [8] on the factors affecting job motivation among faculty members in public universities in Vietnam, they tried to find out how work characteristics, wage and welfare, social recognition, peer relationships, training and promotion opportunities, leader caring, teacher-student interaction and student's attitude, and work motivation affect performance. The results show that all these factors motivate the faculty to perform effectively; thus, the need to consider them.

Another study focusing on the influence of institutional support strategies and faculty job effectiveness in Nigeria was performed by Falola *et al.* [9]. This included research support and pedagogical support. The results imply that, if institutional support is given priority by the management, it will impact significantly on the faculty's level of job performance.

Also, a comparative study was performed by Snook *et al.* [10] on the needs, motivations, and identification with teaching between temporary part-time and tenure-track health science faculty in Iceland. They found out that the environment provided seems to be supporting both sessional faculty (SF) and tenure-track faculty (TF) interest. Also, there was no difference in the identified regulated motivation between SF and TF as the values and beliefs integrated into a teacher were their reasons to teach. Additionally, their results suggested that the SF would be more motivated than TF to reflect on their teaching or try a new teaching method if they are shown forms of appreciation such as general recognition, feedback from supervisors, financial compensation, and improved student evaluations. Lopez and Irene [11] identified the career motivation and commitment to teaching among pre-service teachers at a state university in Samar. Extrinsic motivation factors such as reliable income, steady career path, and security drive these pre-service teachers to continue taking the teaching program, while intrinsic or altruistic factors dominate the commitment to pursue a teaching career.

Given all of these, it is noted that several factors may either motivate or hinder faculty from committing themselves to give their best. These factors are crucial if an institution, including academic or training, wants to accomplish goals. Hence, identifying motivators to effective performance becomes an important component for organizational success. Relative to the current study, it is important that the motivational attributes to perform effectively of the maritime-related institutions be given attention to come up with a systematic and more applicable ODI.

As the country's leading port, Manila Bay hosts the Port of Manila, which consists of three harbors: North Harbor, South Harbor, and the Manila International Container Terminal (MICT). This port serves as a central hub for maritime transportation and commerce [12], thus, the need for security and safety. It is the Philippine Coast Guard (PCG) and the Philippine Navy (PN) that protects the Philippine coasts. They perform several important responsibilities, along with the Philippine Merchant Marine Academy (PMMA) graduates who are reserved or active officers of the PN and active members of the PCG.

Unfortunately, although ODI have been around for some time, its inception in these three institutions has not been fully established. It is for this reason that this study was conceptualized, employing appreciative inquiry, a strengths-based, positive approach to leadership development, and organizational

change. As a result, the study identified the attributes that affect the performance of the training instructors in maritime-related institutions and used them to develop the proposed ODI. Specifically, it answered the following:

- a. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - i) age;
 - ii) sex;
 - iii) years of experience as a training instructor;
 - iv) highest educational attainment;
 - v) salary; and vi) current job/task/responsibility.
- b. What are the training instructors' extent of agreement on the attributes that affect their performance in terms of:
 - i) leadership, goals, and systems;
 - ii) capacity and expertise;
 - iii) personal;
 - iv) welfare;
 - v) task-related;
 - vi) resource-related; and vii) relationship?
- c. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their extent of agreement on the attributes affecting their performance?
- d. What is the degree of importance of the ODI in terms of? i) diagnostic activities; ii) team building activities; iii) intergroup activities; iv) education and training activities; v) techno structural or structural activities; vi) process consultation activities; vii) coaching & counseling activities; viii) life & career planning activities; ix) planning & goal-setting activities; and x) strategic management activities.
- e. Is there a significant difference among the responses of PCG, PMMA and PN on the degree of importance of ODI in their institution?
- f. What are the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of PCG, PMMA, and PN in terms of: i) profile; ii) attributes; and iii) ODI activities?
- g. What proposed validated ODI can be recommended to improve the performance of the training instructors of the maritime-related institutions?

This study is anchored on different theories. Kurt Lewin's Change Management Theory consists of three stages: i) unfreezing: prepare employees for change by raising awareness and addressing concerns; ii) moving: implement changes, guiding and supporting employees through the transition; and iii) refreezing: consolidate changes by engaging employees and reinforcing new behaviors. This theory emphasizes addressing resistance, supporting employees, and reinforcing change for sustainable results [13]. One model utilized in the field of OD to guide planned processes is the appreciative inquiry (AI) model. The original appreciative inquiry method was a collective discovery process into the best of what is, what might be, what should be, and what can be, although various approaches have emerged as time passes [14].

In the current study, particular motivation theories are considered backbone in terms of motivation: i) According to Trivedi and Mehta [15], Maslow's Hierarchy of Human Needs is a pyramid model that organizes human needs into five levels, from basic physiological needs at the bottom to self-actualization at the top, demonstrating that basic needs must be met before pursuing higher-level aspirations; ii) Performance evaluations assess employees' skills and contributions, which is essential for boosting productivity and aligning expectations. By applying Victor Vroom's expectancy theory, organizations can enhance employee motivation and commitment through effective appraisals and rewards, ultimately driving innovation and improving performance [16]; iii) Motivation-hygiene theory, also known as Herzberg's two-factor theory, distinguishes between motivation factors and hygiene factors in relation to job satisfaction. While hygiene factors are necessary for preventing dissatisfaction, they are deemed less critical to overall job satisfaction compared to motivation factors, which significantly influence employee engagement and fulfillment [17]; and iv) Inuwa [18] conducted additional research into Adams' equity theory and concluded that job equity has an impact on employee performance, emphasizing that perceived fairness boosts motivation and morale, and that managers should prioritize equity in decision-making to improve performance and productivity.

Relative to the current study, it is assumed that instructors of these three institutions are motivated by certain factors, from personal to professional. Their needs must be fulfilled to be motivated. And the more motivated they are, the greater is the chance that they would contribute to the success of their institutions. This is supported by the theory of performance (ToP). According to Elger [19], ToP includes the individual or the people working together to produce valued results. Additionally, it discusses that the level of performance depends on context, level of knowledge, level of skills, level of identity, personal factors, and fixed factors. For a holistic view of how this research was pursued, the research paradigm is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research paradigm

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study used the quantitative-descriptive approach. Using the survey, the attributes that motivate the instructors, along with the very important ODI, were identified. Quantifying what exists in the three institutions and establishing statistical relationships were useful in understanding their current view of the variables, which became the basis in designing the proposed output, the ODI.

2.2. Respondents

The respondents of the study were the training instructors of three interrelated maritime agencies, namely Philippine Coast Guard Education, Training, and Doctrine Command (PCG-CGETDC), Philippine Navy Education, Training, and Doctrine Command (PN-NETDC), and Philippine Merchant Marine Academy Training Center or PMMA-TC. Table 1 provides the total population of the training instructors, as well as the number of respondents of the study.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents

Institution	No. of instructors	% sharing	Respondents
PCG-CGETDC	349	77.73	162
PN-NETDC	100	22.27	46
Total	449	100	208
PMMA-TC	7	(Less one for validation)	6
Grand Total	456		214

2.3. Instrument

The instrument for this study is a researcher-made questionnaire. The part which covers motivation is based on the reviewed studies and Swanson's performance diagnosis matrix [20]. The different interventions, on the other hand, are based on Augustine *et al.* [5], and Verghese [6]. The questionnaire was validated by four research experts. The instrument was revised based on their suggestions, then administered to five selected faculty (two from PCG, two from PN, and one from PMMA) who were not part of the final respondents to test its reliability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the items is 0.993, suggesting that the items have relatively high internal consistency.

2.4. Procedure

Initially, the institutions were communicated for permission to be included in the study, which they all agreed to. The data were gathered using the Google form platform. The data collected was processed using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) and interpreted using qualitative interpretation. As with the output of this study, which is the proposed organizational interventions, they were reviewed by an ODI practitioner for comments and suggestions. Then, six expert-representatives from the PCG-CGETDC, PN-NETDC, and PMMA-TC evaluated if each ODI is applicable, purpose-driven, result-oriented, and will be implemented/recommended for implementation in their institution.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Profile of interviewees

Most of the instructors are from ages 40 and below, a total of 82.71% as presented in Table 2. Those with ages 51 and above are merely 1.87%. One possible reason is that as per Section 5.a of the Presidential Decree No. 1638, as amended, an officer or enlisted man shall be compulsory retired upon attaining fifty-six (56) years of age or upon accumulation of thirty (30) years of satisfactory active service. Since the PCG and PN are governed by this, it is assumed that most of those that are 51 years old and above are from the PMMA with their optional retirement age of 60 years old, and mandatory retirement upon reaching 65 years old.

Table 2. Profile of instructor-respondents

	Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age	30 and below	80	37.38
	31-40	97	45.33
	41-50	33	15.42
	51 and above	4	1.87
	Total	214	100.00%
Sex	Male	156	72.90
	Female	58	27.10
	Total	214	100.00%
Years of experience as training instructor	0-3	128	59.81
	4-6	56	26.17
	7-9	14	6.54
	10 and above	16	7.48
	Total	214	100.00%
Highest educational attainment	Undergraduate/vocational	42	19.63
	Bachelor's degree	141	65.89
	Diploma course	17	7.94
	Master's degree	10	4.67
	Doctorate degree	4	1.87
	Total	214	100.00%
Salary	20,000 and below	12	5.61
	21,000-40,000	90	42.06
	41,000-60,000	80	37.38
	61,000-80,000	29	13.55
	81,000 and above	3	1.40
	Total	214	100.00%
Current job/task/responsibility	Training/teaching-related tasks only	88	41.12%
	Administrative function only	27	12.62%
	Both (training/teaching-related tasks with administrative function)	99	46.26%
	Total	214	100.00%

The study by Grimett [21], citing the International Maritime Organization, highlights that women encounter significant challenges in various aspects of their work. The underrepresentation of women in the maritime industry is concerning, leading scholars and organizations to emphasize the need for greater inclusion of women across all employment sectors. As with the military, it was only in 1992 that women were allowed to join in the military ranks as stated in Section 7 of Republic Act No. 7192. At the PMMA, the first batch of women graduates was in 1997. It is, therefore, assumed that the number of women in these maritime-related institutions is lower than men, both in seafaring and in military ranks, since women integration and empowerment is relatively new.

As with the years of experience as training instructors, it can be gleaned from Table 2 that most of the respondents have 0-3 years' experience, with 59.81% while the 7 and above years of experience is 14.02%. As most of the instructor-respondents are from the younger generation, it follows that they also have shorter years of experience as training instructors. In terms of educational attainment, it is noted that most of the respondents, 65.89%, are bachelor's degree holders. As there were instructors who are undergraduate/vocational, verification was made to the PCG and PN. Accordingly, these are enlisted personnel teaching the pre-entry course, basic specialization course, and the like, but before teaching these, they were equipped with training and education related to the courses they are to teach. The PMMA, being an educational institution, requires a minimum educational requirement of bachelor's degree; thus, not included in the inquiry.

As with the salary, most of the respondents fall from 21,000 to 60,000, with a combined percentage of 79.44% while a few receive 61,000 and above (14.95%), and only 5.61% receives 20,000 and below. Part of those who fall in the latter could be the part-time instructors at the PMMA because they are paid by the hour and only when they have training assignments. Currently, many of the instructors are either teaching, with 41.12%, or multi-tasking, with 46.26%. This implies that since a larger number of the instructor-

respondents are doing multiple tasks, their performance can also be affected. This is supported by the study of Liu *et al.* [22] that the multi-role tasks have caused serious work stress on the respondents, which resulted in employee turnover. Additionally, David *et al.* [23] found out that having administrative tasks, in addition to teaching, affected his respondents' performance.

3.2. Extent of agreement on the attributes affecting performance

Table 3 summarizes the attributes that were given high extent of agreement by the instructor-respondents in terms of motivating them to perform effectively. Over-all, the instructor-respondents are highly motivated to perform by 31 out of 40 different attributes. Social factors such as relationships with co-workers, group working and norms, opportunities for interaction and informal relations, relationship with head of department and with top management or supervision, prompt feedback and communication received from management and seniors, participation in decision making, autonomy, empowerment, the amount of praise received for outstanding efforts, the opportunity to voice their opinion result to job satisfaction and eventually improve job performance [24].

Table 3. Summary of attributes with high extent of agreement

Attributes	High extent of agreement
Leadership, goals and systems	1. My professional goals are aligned with the organizational goals.
	2. There is open communication between head and subordinates.
	3. Fair work practices such as no favoritism, and equal opportunities for all, are observed.
	4. There is technical support, such as providing assistance in using the internet or laptops, or setting up the laboratory.
	5. Selection, recruitment and promotion policies are clear and in-place.
	6. There is evaluation and feedback system.
	7. There is a quality management system in place.
Capacity and expertise	8. There is emotional readiness to perform the assigned job/task.
	9. The educational qualifications are related to the job/task.
	10. There is knowledge about the job/tasks.
	11. The skills are present to perform the job/tasks.
Personal	12. There are experiences that help in performing the job/task.
	13. Personal commitment to duties and responsibilities is present.
	14. The management considers and respects personal matters and support, such as family matters and health issues.
Welfare	15. There is stable job and job security.
	16. Acceptable salary is received.
	17. Fringe benefits (such as research honoraria, communication allowance, and transportation allowance) are provided.
	18. Reward system such as appreciation and recognition are present.
	19. Training packages for development are offered.
	20. Promotion opportunities are existing.
Task-related	21. Job feedback (being evaluated and informed on areas for improvement, if there is) is performed.
	22. There are clearly identified tasks (task identity).
	23. I find the task provided to me important.
Resource-related	24. Adequate physical facilities such as building, lab, training vessel, simulators, and other facilities are provided.
	25. Technological aid such as laptops, are available.
	26. Work areas/spaces are conducive.
Relationship	27. There is social recognition/belongingness in the group.
	28. Peer relationship is pleasant.
	29. There is mutual respect between head and the staff.
	30. There is good and safe working environment.
	31. There is job cooperation within the team.

3.3. Significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their extent of agreement on the attributes affecting performance

Based on the results, age was found to be with no significant relationship with any of the attributes. However, when the relationship per indicator was computed, it was found to have a significant negative relationship with the attribute's welfare and resource-related indicators, specifically fringe benefits, promotion opportunities, sufficient provision of supplies, and clearly identified tasks. This means that as they grow older, their desire for welfare and resource-related attributes decreases. As Wong and Tetrick [25] explained, the idea of limited time remaining in their careers drives older workers to focus on fewer but specific outcomes that would provide immediate gratification.

Sex has no significant relationship with any of the attributes. However, when the relationship per indicator was computed, it was found that it has a significant relationship with the indicator "work areas/spaces are conducive." This shows that employed women and men tend to see the workplace differently, with women leaning more toward the pessimistic view and men more toward the optimistic view [26].

As per institution, this has a significant relationship with Resource-related, specifically with the indicator "work areas/spaces are conducive". As with workspace arrangements, Al-Omari and Okasheh [27]

found out that the physical environment at work is critical to employees' performance, satisfaction, social relations, and health. They suggested that employers should take initiatives to motivate employees by improving their work environment.

Over-all, the years of experience (YoE) as training instructor has a significant relationship with a single attribute-relationship. However, statistical tests show that it has a significant relationship with several other indicators. Under leadership, goals, and systems, "selection, recruitment, and promotion policies are clear and in-place." Widiani and Wayan [28] stated that experience is related to promotion because having a lot of job experience will help individuals complete their tasks without waiting for orders. Since they have been performing well brought by their experiential learning, they look forward to promotion. Under capacity and expertise "there is emotional readiness to perform the assigned job/task; while under resource-related "technological aid such as laptops, are available" and "the office supplies are provided" were found to have a significant relationship with YoE. This implies that as the length of service increases, the instructor-respondents become emotionally ready, require more technological assistance, and aspire for good teamwork.

Employees will be satisfied and motivated if they are paid or an increment in salary is given. This means an increase in the amount of current salary will lead to an increase in work performance as well. Salary is a benchmark often used by employees as a means of their contribution to the organization they are working for, and they regard it as their value to the particular organization [29]. The significant relationship of salary was tested with the attributes, and it was found to have a significant relationship with six attributes. It is noted from the findings that as the salary increases, the desire to have delegative and participative leadership, better communication and relationship, professional development, promotion, and quality supplies also increases.

The highest educational attainment was found to have a significant relationship with the attribute leadership, goals & systems, and task-related. A higher education leads to increased earning potential and better opportunities for career. Thus, it is expected that this also increases one's aspiration of clear and attainable goals, better treatment, and practices.

Results of Pearson r correlation test revealed that the current job/tasks/responsibilities have a significant relationship with five attribute-categories, namely: leadership, goals, and systems, capacity and expertise, welfare, task-related, and relationship. However, it was found to have a significant relationship with one indicator under personal and three under resource related. This implies that the instructor-respondents look at a complete package where everything is in place, from goals to policies to physical environment and relationships to supplies, and all others.

3.4. Degree of importance of the ODI

Under diagnostic activities, there were five activities that were considered very important and four which are important. Over-all, however, this received a mean of 3.26, which means that the activity is rated very important. As Allen [30] stated, a diagnostic survey provides a method suitable for several topics and specializations in different areas of knowledge, and it is one of the best methods to gather the largest amount of data from participants.

Team building, on the other hand, has a sub-mean of 3.25. It can be noted in Table 4 that it is the PMMA Training instructors that provided a lower degree of importance to these activities. It could be that some of them are part-timers and do not expect to be included when activities related to these are organized. Cletus *et al.* [31] found in their study that team building is crucial in any modern-day institution. Its implementation enables employees to flourish and establish mutual trust regardless of their level of diversity and can help them connect and communicate more effectively, or even "break the ice".

Similarly, Cross-group activities are only considered important by majority of the respondents. This, however, is a very important ODI because it allows exposure of instructors to other members of the institution. As with the activities on education and training, techno structural or structural, process consultation, coaching & counseling, life & career planning, planning & goal-setting activities and strategic management, they are all considered very important by the instructor-respondents.

Among all the ODI categories, it is the Education and Training activities that received the highest mean of 3.50. As Rodriguez and Walters [32] found, employee training and development assists the organization and employees in attaining diverse goals. It is safe to say that the more educated and skillful the employees are, the better chance that they would become instruments to change and development too. This is followed by the categories planning & goal-setting activities and coaching & counseling activities. According to Serrat [33], coaching and mentoring can be used whenever performance or motivation levels need to be increased. Moreover, Raza *et al.* [34] found in their study that employees thrive at work when their manager acts as a coach, openly communicates with subordinates, accept ideas of others, supports the individual's needs, and rely on team approach to enhance their subordinates.

Per institution, the PCG gave the highest mean of 3.53 for training opportunities. This importance has been repeatedly mentioned, even on attributes that highly motivate the instructors to perform effectively. On the other hand, the PN has the highest mean of 3.59 for activities that help them focus on their life and

career and achieve them. In the literature review made by Bawa [35], he laid the fifth practical implication, which is to take a personal interest in the social life of subordinates by supporting them in other aspects of their lives outside work. The management can also consider flexible working hours for employees to focus on their family or to pursue further studies. Accordingly, when the management does this, the workers will feel happy with the company, and they will see the failure of the company as their own failure.

With PMMA, the instructor-respondents considered institutional strategic planning and scholarship as very important ODI with the highest mean of 3.67. As Paraggua *et al.* [36] mentioned in their study, a strategic plan aids in defining what an institution intends to achieve when it comes to their student success objectives and organizational goals. Accordingly, universities and colleges devote time and effort in strategic plans to assist their institution's direction. Overall, there were 23 activities that are considered very important while the remaining seven are important. These should be given attention as they are useful in motivating the instructors to perform effectively.

Table 4. Degree of importance of ODI

ODI intervention	PCG-CGETDC	PN-NETDC	PMMA-TC	MEAN	QI
A. Diagnostic activities to identify issues and problems such as:					
1. Gathering of secondary data (tax records, and census)	3.33	3.50	3.17	3.33	Vi
2. Observation of people at work	3.46	3.46	3.33	3.42	Vi
3. Distribution of questionnaires to selected subjects	3.33	3.57	3.00	3.30	Vi
4. Conducting individual interviews	3.25	3.52	3.50	3.42	Vi
5. Conducting sensing or unstructured group interview	3.12	3.26	3.17	3.18	I
6. Polling of opinions and attitudes	3.27	3.28	2.83	3.13	I
7. Diagnostic team meetings	3.43	3.35	3.17	3.32	Vi
8. Collating and drawing	3.34	3.57	2.83	3.25	I
9. Confrontation meetings	3.21	3.24	2.50	2.98	I
Sub-mean	3.31	3.42	3.06	3.26	Vi
B. Team building activities that will bring team members closer and improve teamwork and collaboration such as:					
1. Indoor activities	3.30	3.43	3.00	3.24	I
2. Outdoor activities	3.39	3.57	2.83	3.26	Vi
Sub-mean*	3.34ab	3.50b	2.92a	3.25	I
C. Cross-group activities like teams 1 and 2 doing a single task; allows individuals to work with other units/departments)					
	3.20	3.28	2.67	3.05	I
D. Education and training activities such as:					
1. 1. Scholarship	3.30	3.41	3.67	3.46	Vi
2. 2. Training opportunities	3.53	3.61	3.50	3.55	Vi
Sub-mean	3.42	3.51	3.58	3.50	Vi
E. Techno structural or structural activities such as:					
1. Workspace arrangements	3.40	3.50	3.00	3.30	Vi
2. Operating procedures	3.41	3.61	3.33	3.45	Vi
3. Role definition	3.42	3.61	3.17	3.40	Vi
Sub-mean	3.41	3.57	3.17	3.38	Vi
F. Process consultation activities such as:					
1. Inclusion in problem solving and decision making	3.44	3.54	3.00	3.33	Vi
2. Open communication	3.39	3.59	3.00	3.33	Vi
3. Importance of roles in the process	3.50	3.50	3.33	3.44	Vi
Sub-mean	3.44	3.54	3.11	3.36	Vi
G. Coaching & counseling activities					
1. Coaching activities	3.45	3.54	3.17	3.39	Vi
2. Counseling activities	3.40	3.59	3.50	3.50	Vi
Sub-mean	3.42	3.57	3.33	3.44	Vi
H. Life & career planning activities such as:					
1. Activities that enable individuals to focus on their life and career objectives & find ways to achieve them	3.38	3.59	3.17	3.38	Vi
2. Matching individual goals with the organizational goals to for mutual benefit	3	4	3	3.37	Vi
Sub-mean	3.37	3.55	3.17	3.36	Vi
I. Planning & goal-setting activities					
1. Division/department/unit/section level planning session	3.43	3.61	3.50	3.51	Vi
2. Midyear performance & year-end assessment session	3.48	3.54	3.33	3.45	Vi
3. Preparation of individual performance commitments	3.35	3.50	3.17	3.34	Vi
Sub-mean	3.42	3.55	3.34	3.44	Vi
J. Strategic management activities					
1. SWOT analysis	3.23	3.43	3.33	3.33	Vi
2. Agency/institution strategic planning session	3.38	3.43	3.67	3.49	Vi
Sub-mean	3.31	3.43	3.50	3.41	Vi
Mean	3.36	3.49	3.19	3.35	Vi

Legend: 1.0-1.75 – Not important, 1.76-2.50 – Somewhat important, 2.56-3.25 – Important, 3.26-4.00 – Very important

3.5. Significant difference in the degree of importance of ODI of the institutions

There were three ODI activities where significant differences were noted. First is under diagnostic activities, which is “collating and drawing of issues/problems.” A Bonferroni Post Hoc Test revealed a significant difference in the responses of PN and PMMA respondents (p=0.043). This activity could be significant with the PN as they are in-charge of trainees who would ensure the safety and security in the country. With PMMA, the intensity may not be as extensive as that of the PN since most of their trainees are for ship operations. Another is under team building activities, which is “outdoor activities.” A Bonferroni Post Hoc Test revealed a significant difference in the responses of PN and PMMA respondents (p=0.013). It is emphasized that most of the PMMA training instructors are part-timers. Thus, they are commonly excluded from outdoor activities. As with the case of the activity “open communication,” the Bonferroni Post Hoc Test showed that there is no significant difference between the responses as its p-value is greater than 0.05 level. To validate, the data was run using Jamovi, which provided the p-value of 0.033, similar to the one-way ANOVA test result. Then, the Tukey HSD was performed to validate this result, and the same finding was revealed. As such, the significant difference is considered very weak that a post hoc test or the Tukey cannot verify the difference.

3.6. SWOT analysis of results and other related data

The strengths-weaknesses-opportunities-threats (SWOT) analysis was performed. This strategy was considered crucial in identifying areas that need addressing. Other possible data that were useful in the creation of the ODI, which is proposed, are also included in Table 5 (see appendix).

3.7. Proposed validated ODI for PCG-CGETDC, PN-NETDC, and PMMA-TC

A vital consideration in this proposal is the creation of the OD unit, which will be under the human resource management office. Its main task is to implement and institutionalize the ODI, with the goal to improve participation and performance towards institutional efficiency and effectiveness through research-based ODI. Additionally, it is beneficial to have proper information, education, and assistance to address the possible issue of selectively implementing the proposed interventions since ODI is something new for a few, and that change entails resistance.

The proposed interventions and strategies are divided into two matrices to capture all findings, namely: i) ODI responding to identified weaknesses and threats, and ii) ODI based on those considered by instructor-respondents as high motivators and significant ODI. To ensure implement ability, each matrix has the following parts: current issue or highly motivating attributes (HMA) and very important ODI (VI-ODI); intervention; strategy, resources (personnel & estimated cost); key result area; duration/timeframe; and evaluation measures for executability reasons. However, only the first four columns are included in this manuscript due to space limitation. For ODI Program Matrix 1, there are ten identified issues to be addressed by the proposed ODI, as presented in Table 6. On the other hand, Table 7 presents nine categories that could highly propel the performance of the instructors.

Table 6. Proposed intervention for current issues

Identified weaknesses and threats	Objective	Intervention	Strategy
Male-dominated institutions	To improve hiring and promotion process through training	Diversity	Unconscious bias training for human resource personnel
Short number of years of experience	To revise the current rewards manual by the end of the 2022	Reward systems	Review and revise current manual on rewards using benchmarking and gap analysis
Most of the instructors are bachelor's degree holder	To provide post-grad scholarships to 5 instructors every two years	Empowerment and career planning	Master's degree scholarship
Some instructors are undergraduate	To provide trainers training	Empowerment and career planning	IMO MC 6.09 training, IMO MC 3.12 training, and IMO MC 6.10 training
Multi-tasking	To establish a basis for decision making on multi-tasking	Diagnostic	Survey
Some instructors approaching retirement	To establish a smooth transition process	Empowerment and career planning	Succession planning
Budget-and process-related issue	To ensure funding for the ODI implementation	MBO and QMS	Strategic planning
Non-implementation of ODI by the implementers	To create awareness on ODI	Awareness	Awareness seminar
No Plantilla positions	To increase motivation through job security	Empowerment and career planning	Proposal on Plantilla creation
Inconsistent implementation of evaluation systems and weak evaluation instrument	To improve the evaluation instrument and its implementation	Evaluation and feedback	Review, revise, and implementation

Table 7. Proposed intervention for identified very important ODI and indicators that highly motivate the respondents

HMA & VI-ODI	Objective	Intervention	Strategy
Qualification & development	To provide education and training related to maritime tasks	1. Empowerment and career planning 2. Job Enrichment	PhD scholarship Job rotation
Readiness & commitment	To increase readiness and commitment to tasks and responsibilities	Empowerment and career planning	Training of coaches Creation of coaching manual
Personal welfare and rewards	1. To create a motivational package for employees 2. To improve health and wellness	Reward systems Wellness program	Benchmarking of other institution's practices Gap analysis of what exists and does not to come up with the best institutional reward systems Create guidelines on its coverage and procedures Athletics day Stress management seminar Mental health seminar
Social-related	To improve relationships and teamwork	1. Team building 2. Diversity	Sensitivity/ diversity training Diversity career page on the website Diverse mentorships & counseling Creation of Inclusion council Diversity day Strengthen anti-discriminatory policies by incorporating diversity into company policies and practices
Policies, process & systems	To improve the process and procedural systems in operations	1. QMS 2. Process consultation	Risk-based approach Management review Process consultation
Planning-related	To ensure the achievement of organizational goals	MBO	SWOT through survey Strategic planning
Task-related	To motivate employees using task identity and job importance	1. Job enrichment 2. Role analysis and negotiation	Job redesigning Role analysis and negotiation
Physical Environment	To improve the physical facilities and workspaces	Technological	Assessment Maintenance plan Creation of land use development & infrastructure plan (LUDIP)
Evaluation-related	To implement a standardized evaluation and feedback system	Feedback and evaluation	Survey

4. CONCLUSION

The current pool of training instructors of the PCG-CGETDC, PN-NETDC, and the PMMA-TC are equipped with desirable knowledge, competence, skills, and work values. Their strengths and weaknesses have similarities and differences. At the same time, they are highly motivated by different performance attributes. They have similar views and are open to development as they find many OD interventions valuable. These results were useful inputs in the development of the output. Upon the inclusion of all necessary data and the validation of experts from the three institutions, the proposed validated ODI can be readily implemented.

APPENDIX

Table 5. Summary of strengths-weaknesses-opportunities-threats

Determinants	List of strengths-weaknesses-opportunities-threats
Strengths	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Many of the instructors are of young age, 40 years old and below Acceptable salary ranging from 21,000 to 60,000 pesos Very good performance based on latest evaluation results Identified individual and collective attributes that highly motivate the PCG, PN and PMMA training instructors Some of the profiles were of significant relationship with a few of the attributes. Identified ODI considered very important Educational scholarships provided to the instructors and other staff Modernization programs exist at the PCG and the PN Promotion at PCG and PN are in place

Table 5. Summary of strengths-weaknesses-opportunities-threats (continue)

Determinants	List of strengths-weaknesses-opportunities-threats
Weaknesses	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maritime is male-dominated 2. Short number of years of experience 3. Maritime is male-dominated 4. Short number of years of experience 5. Most of the instructors are bachelor's degree holder, with only 6.54% with post-graduate; while 19.63% are undergraduate (42 out of 214) 6. Multi-tasked instructors 7. Some attributes moderately stimulate them to perform that affect achieving goals, autocratic leadership common to military, and adjustment to tasks diversity 8. Some ODI such as cross group activities and confrontation meetings considered as only important 9. PMMA training instructors have considered many of the ODI as only important 10. No Plantilla position for PMMA-TC 11. Inconsistent implementation of evaluation system at PCG 12. PMMA-TC evaluation instrument needs revision 13. Limited scholarships
Opportunities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CHED provides scholarship 2. ODI consultants are available and can be contacted via online platform <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Young generation as instructors is a helpful assurance that if they are given the right education, training and experience, these institutions will have a pool of capable instructors b. Identified strengths, the institutions can take advantage of that information to come up with a win-win solution in motivating their instructors c. Aligning ODI with the identified motivators could result to a better proposal for OD interventions <p>Openness to development of the frontrunners of change of these institutions</p>
Threats	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lucrative jobs abroad could lure many officers and enlisted men to resign or retire early resulting to high employee turnover 2. Government budget cuts resulting to inadequate or no funding for the ODI program <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Some instructors approaching retirement b. High turnover due to number of instructors who are receiving below 20,000 pesos per month c. Number of female recruits is still minimal as compared to their male counterparts d. Budget- and process-related. Some of the motivators require expenditures e. Non-acceptance and non-implementation of the implementers to ODI f. OD interventions are not institutionalized <p>PMMA-TC focused on in-house training, limiting possible source of income in implementing ODI</p>

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